

Proton-Ligand Stability Constants of some Amino Acids**

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Proton-ligand stability constant of hippuric acid as also of glycine, α and β -alanine determined by the method of Irving-Rossotti in 50% V/V ethanol-water mixture at 30° and 0.1 ionic-strength have been reported. The $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ values for the three amino acids have also been reinvestigated in water medium under similar conditions. The differences of stability constant values in the mixed solvent and water are fairly positive in case of $\log K_2^H$ (for carboxylic proton) and slightly negative in case of $\log K_1^H$, as expected. In case of β -alanine, $\log K_2^H$ value is higher than that of the α -isomer due to the increased distance of the amino and the carboxylic groups. The pK^* value for hippuric acid as computed by half-integral and graphical method has been found to be 4.3 at 30° and 0.1 ionic strength.

IN dicumarol and other anticoagulant therapy using rare-earth salts for thrombotic diseases, hippuric acid test is utilised as a diagnostic tool for testing liver-function and its capacity to synthesize some of the blood-coagulant factors¹. In order to study the metal-binding capacity, particularly of some biologically active metal ions by hippuric acid, benzoyl glycine, we have undertaken some studies of the nature of dissociation of hippuric acid. In our present paper we have reported the proton-ligand stability constant of hippuric acid using pH-titration technique of Bjerrun-Calvin as modified by Irving-Rossotti² in 50% V/V ethanol-water mixture as the compound is only sparingly soluble in water. Although values of $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ for different amino acids have been worked out by various authors through different techniques and are available in standard literature³, the data for glycine, α - and β -alanine under same conditions have been parallelly presented in the present communication with a view to having a comparative and correlative idea of the protonation of hippuric acid by the same technique.

Experimental

Materials: Double-distilled water was used. Ethanol was purified before use by the standard method⁴. Perchloric acid used was of AR grade (E. M. Company). Carbonate-free alkali solution was prepared using AR grade sodium hydroxide pellets. Perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions were standardised potentiometrically against standard solution of potassium-hydrogen-phthalate.

The amino acids were of AR grade and their purity was tested by the method of formol-titration⁵. Their solutions were prepared in 50% V/V ethanol-

water mixture. Sodium perchlorate (pure) solution used to maintain constant ionic strength was standardised by estimating the perchloric acid obtained after passing the solution through Amberlite IR-120(H-form) resin.

Procedure: pH-titrations were performed with two sets of solutions; (i) Perchloric acid+sodium perchlorate; (ii) Perchloric acid+amino acid+sodium perchlorate, the total volume being 50 ml in each set. Constant ionic strength of 0.1 was maintained by adding required volume of sodium perchlorate solution. The final concentration of Perchloric acid and amino acids were $3.2 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ respectively. The alkali used was 0.58M.

Measurements were done at $30^\circ \pm 0.5$ using Beckman glass-electrode of 0-14 pH range in conjunction with SCE connected by means of an agar-2M sodium nitrate bridge.⁶

From the titration curves of free acid and (free acid+amino acid), the average number of protons associated with amino acids (\bar{n}_A) were calculated using the formula of Irving-Rossotti² :-

$$\bar{n}_A = y - \frac{(v'' - v')(N^0 + E^0)}{(V^0 + v'')TC^0_L} \quad \dots (1)$$

where v' & v'' are the volumes of alkali required to reach the same pH in free acid and free acid+amino acid titration curves respectively, N^0 , E^0 and TC^0_L are the initial concentrations of alkali, perchloric acid and amino acids respectively, y is the number of dissociable protons in amino acids, V^0 is the initial volume of the solutions.

The formation curves were drawn by plotting the \bar{n}_A values against their corresponding pH and

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the stability constants were determined by half-integral method. The acid dissociation constant (pK^*) of hippuric acid has also been computed by graphical method using the formula.

$$pH = \log \frac{1 - \bar{n}_A}{\bar{n}_A} + pK^* \quad \dots (2)$$

Results and Discussion

With a view to extending the method of Irving-Rossotti in case of amino acids and obtaining the $\log K_s^H$ value of the carboxylic proton in lower pH -region, we have used more than one equimolecular amounts of perchloric acid compared to amino acids so that the amino acids exist as $\overset{+}{N}H_3RCOOH$ form. In such condition, the pH values of the initial solutions have been higher than the free strong acid because of the protonation of the basic $-COO^-$ group and the dipolar ion has been converted to the acid form, $\overset{+}{N}H_3RCOOH$. This trend is observed till the acid form has completely been converted into the dipolar ion $\overset{+}{N}H_3RCOO^-$ (Figs. 1 & 2). In this region of the titration curves, ($v' > v''$) and we have calculated \bar{n}_A by rearranging the equation (1) which comes out as :

$$\bar{n}_A = y + \frac{(v' - v'')(N^0 + E^0)}{(V^0 + v')TC^0_Z}$$

In higher pH regions, values of $\bar{n}_A < 1$ are obtained

Fig. 1 Titration curves of amino acids in water medium

- : Strong acid
- ⊗- : Strong acid + glycine
- : Strong acid + α -alanine
- : Strong acid + β -alanine.

Fig. 2 Titration curves of amino acids in 50% V/V ethanol-water medium.

- : Strong acid
- ⊗- : Strong acid + glycine
- : Strong acid + α -alanine
- : Strong acid + β -alanine.

Fig. 3 Titration curve of hippuric acid and strong acid in 50% V/V ethanol-water medium.

- : Strong acid
- ⊗- : Strong acid + hippuric acid.

by the use of equation (1) where $v'' > v'$. The \bar{n}_A values thus obtained extends over a range $0.2 < \bar{n}_A < 2.0$ and are plotted against pH values (Figs. 4 & 5) wherefrom the $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ are determined by the method of half-integral at the points $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively.

From the formation curves of amino acids in water and in ethanol-water mediums, it can be seen that $\log K_2^H$ values are markedly increased in ethanol-water medium than those in water medium (Figs. 4 & 5) due to the lowering of dielectric constant of the mixed solvent where the dissociation of proton is negatively favoured and thereby giving higher stability-constant values (Table 1). On the

TABLE-1

(Temp = $30^\circ \pm 0.5$; $\mu = 0.1$)

	$\log K_1^H$		$\log K_2^H$	
	Water	50% V/V ethanol-water	Water	50% V/V ethanol-water
Glycine	9.75	9.25	2.25	2.75
α -alanine	9.85	9.50	2.30	3.15
β -alanine	9.7	9.55	3.60	3.95
Hippuric acid	—	—	—	4.8(a) 4.8(b)

(a) by the method of half-integral
(b) pK^* determined by graphical method.

other hand, there is no such marked change in $\log K_1^H$ values as the role of dielectric constant of the mixed-solvent is less effective in comparison with much increased OH^- concentration of the system, at the higher pH -region. Our observation is consistent with the earlier observations on the nature of such variations in mixed-solvent of different composition^{7,8}.

The $\log K_2^H$ values of α - and β -alanine respectively are 3.15 and 3.95 in 50% V/V ethanol-water and 2.3 and 3.6 in water (Table 1). The higher value in the case of β -isomer is due obviously to the less-effective influence of β -amino group on the dissociation of the carboxylic proton, as a result of the increased distance of the two poles. Such a role of distance on the dissociation has, however, been observed in case of long-chain amino acids like ω -amino acids⁹.

Thomas & Nieman¹⁰ indicated from cryoscopic studies that there is a small but significant amount of diprotonation of the amino acids in absolute sulphuric acid. From Figs. 4 & 5, it can be seen that the values of \bar{n}_A reached to about 2 at a pH near 2. These values indicate that the acid form of the amino acids, NH_3^+RCOOH , can still take up proton in perchloric acid medium, at such a low pH , and diprotonation is a possibility, in accordance with the following reaction :

In the case of titration of hippuric acid, the titration curve of perchloric acid + hippuric acid and

that of perchloric alone practically coincide (Fig. 3) up to pH until the strong acid is fully neutralised. The carboxylic group of the hippuric acid do not form the conjugate base $-COO^-$ intramolecularly indicating practically the absence of any dipolar

Fig. 4 Formation curves of amino acids in water medium.

⊙: Glycine
●: α -alanine
○: β -alanine.

Fig. 5 Formation curves of amino acids in 50% V/V ethanol-water medium.

⊙: Glycine
●: α -alanine
○: β -alanine

form. There is only one inflection in the combined strong acid hippuric acid curve (Fig. 3) indicating the dissociation of only of the carboxylic proton.

The \bar{n}_A values for hippuric acid are calculated from the titration curves by equation (1) and are plotted against pH when $\log K^H$ determined by half-integral method at the point $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ has been found to be 4.3 (Fig. 6). The graphical method is also applied to calculate pK^* by equation (2) where $\log \frac{1-\bar{n}_A}{\bar{n}_A}$ are plotted against pH and pK^* determined from the intercept of the straight line is 4.3 (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 Formation curves of hippuric acid.

- : Half-integral method
 -○- : Graphical method.

From the curve, it is thus evident that there is but slight probability of the hippuric acid to exist in a form like $C_6H_5CONH_2CH_2COO^-$ as the benzoyl group withdrawing electron-density from around the nitrogen, reduces its electron-pair-donor-capacity and accordingly protonation of $-NH$ -group is expected least.

The pK^* value of hippuric acid reported in the present communication is evidently less than the pK value of acetic acid ($pK=4.76$). This small increase in dissociation may, however, be due to the presence of $-NH$ -group which has the capacity, even to a little extent, to pull proton from the carboxyl group, a phenomenon absent in the case of acetic acid. On the other hand, pK value of acetyl glycine which is much raised than that of glycine, i.e., from 2.75 for glycine (in 50% V/V ethanol-

water) to 3.7 for acetyl glycine^{3,11} due to the electron-withdrawing tendency of the acetyl group. Phenyl group being more electron-withdrawing, (enhances the electron-withdrawing) capacity of C_6H_5CO -group. Thus the proton-ligand stability value of hippuric acid is increased than that of acetyl glycine as evidenced from the pK^* value of 4.3 for benzoyl glycine reported by us.

From the data presented in this paper for glycine and hippuric acid in 50% V/V ethanol-water medium (Table 1) and from the standard dissociation constant values for acetyl glycine and acetic acid, the proton-ligand stability constants (for carboxylic proton) may be arranged, as expected in the following order :

Glycine < acetyl glycine < benzoyl glycine < acetic acid
 2.75* < 3.7 < 4.3* < 4.76

* (in 50% V/V ethanol-water)

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